

Sodalite

Software Defined AppLication Infrastructures management and Engineering

Web presence, Branding and Communication guidelines - Final version

D7.1

ATOS

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List of Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
AOE	Application Ops Expert The equivalent process from the ISO/IEC/IEEE standard 12207 Systems and software engineering – Software life cycle processes is Operation processes and maintenance processes
ATOS	Atos Spain S.A
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IaC	Infrastructure as Code
ICT	Information & Communication Technologies
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
QE	Quality Expert The equivalent process from ISO/IEC/IEEE standard 12207 Systems and software engineering – Software life cycle processes: Infrastructure management and Configuration management processes
PC	Project Coordinator
RE	Resource Expert The equivalent process from ISO/IEC/IEEE standard 12207 Systems and software engineering – Software life cycle processes is Quality Management and Quality assurance processes
ToC	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package
Y1	Year one, first year of the project

Acknowledgement

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Disclaimer

The communication and dissemination procedures that are here described follow the Atos methodology used in all H2020 projects where Atos Spain is involved.

Abstract

This document provides a wide view of the extent of communication and dissemination strategy of SODALITE, during 36 months of the project duration.

Furthermore, a detailed list of channels, media and tools used to manage properly the objectives of this strategy is provided. Moreover, this version reveals information about the WP7, where Communication and Dissemination activities are included, due to this content is also needed to understand the sense of Communication and Dissemination across the whole project. Twitter, marketing printed material, Website, conferences, press releases, among others are presented in the document, as well.

Finally, conclusions and references are available to conclude with this document.

Executive Summary

This deliverable is the first version of a comprehensive plan for the communication and dissemination strategy, the respective activities to be planned in the first year (Y1) and the criteria to be employed for their evaluation.

The document provides the main principles of the dissemination and communication strategy to be adopted throughout the Project duration, emphasizing actions to be implemented during Y1. The main interest of using Communication and Dissemination tools is to give, to the greatest extent possible, increased visibility of the project, generate impact in and out the consortium as well as around its network and finally, at a technical level, to generate knowledge diffusion and facilitate community building. Furthermore, the communication and dissemination plan gathers information in accordance with the Communication and Dissemination strategy. The targeted demographics and objectives to be fulfilled are part of this plan, as well. To achieve these objectives, the plan is divided into on-line and off-line strategies that include the following:

- the participation in relevant events, i.e. conferences, public sector and industry events, academic and research events, seminars and information days, as well as the organization of project dedicated events,
- the production of relevant material, comprising communication materials (e.g. logo, project presentation, newsletters, press releases, leaflets, poster, etc.) that bear the project's graphical identity and convey its main messages and goals, as well as scientific publications,
- the management and exploitation of several electronic and web dissemination channels, including the project website, its collaboration portal and social media accounts, but also
- the implementation of appropriate liaison activities in collaboration with other relevant projects and adjacent communities.

Particular emphasis is also placed on the way the former tools map to the targeted audiences and their anticipated impact.

The actual Communication and Dissemination Plan has been developed to reach, on one hand, specific communication and, on the other hand, dissemination objectives, with great efficiency.

A dedicated section of the document further sets out the approach for monitoring and evaluating the dissemination and communication activities, including key performance indicators, against which the effectiveness of both dissemination and communication activities will be assessed.

Finally, the document shows the role played by every partner in communication and dissemination activities. This point is important because it reveals the efforts that each partner will provide across the project duration. Project partners play a key enabling role in building a community around SODALITE and further reinforce the results of the overall Communication and Dissemination strategy.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of this document

The present deliverable (D7.1) entitled “Web presence, branding and communication guidelines” is particularly associated with T7.2 “Dissemination and Evangelization” of WP7 and, as such, its main purpose is to define the SODALITE dissemination and communication strategy that will ensure, both through conventional means (i.e. conferences, workshops, website, etc.) and online ones (e.g. social media and website), high levels of engagement for the various identified SODALITE stakeholders. Therefore, targeted activities are considered and planned initially at the present deliverable. Throughout the project, close collaboration with experts, private companies, non-governmental organizations, as well as with other projects and initiatives is sought.

Along the above lines, the present deliverable aims to fulfil the following main objectives:

- To define a strategy for the project’s dissemination and communication activities.
- To introduce a series of roles and responsibilities for these activities.
- To identify the channels and tools to be used for the dissemination of the project’s knowledge (i.e. events, dissemination material and online channels).
- To recognize the dissemination opportunities in international events and conferences for the next months of the project’s duration.
- To set the social media strategy for the community and an initial blog post and newsletter plan in order to ensure a successful online presence in Web 2.0 platforms.
- To identify liaison opportunities with other projects & communities and start creating synergies.
- To set the methodology under which the evaluation of dissemination and communication activities will be accomplished.

Dissemination and communication are concerned with making the project visible, creating awareness and understanding of the project and promoting participation in the project. Therefore, a dissemination strategy needs to address the following issues:

- The **Aim** of dissemination: objectives (section 2; Dissemination and Communication Overview-Statement)
- **What** will be disseminated: outcomes (section 2; Dissemination and Communication Overview-Statement)
- **Who** is the audience: target groups (section 2; Dissemination and Communication Overview-Statement)
- **What** medium will be used: resources & channels (section 3/4 Off-line and On-line strategy).
- **When** it will be disseminated: timing (First year of the project, Y1)

1.2 Structure of the document and relation with other WPs

The document will follow this structure in the next sections:

- Section 2 presents the whole Communication and Dissemination plan with its respective strategy what includes activities, media, tools, participant roles and audience.
- Section 3 is the concrete off-line strategy of SODALITE, including material and activities to be developed during Y1.

- Section 4, on the contrary, is all the On-line strategy, including media and activities settled to be developed through on-line channels in Y1.
- Section 5 gathers every event planned by the consortium to attend in the following Y1 and besides every publication, scientific or for general audiences scheduled to be submitted.
- Section 6 is the chapter where every partner explains with further details its contribution to the Communication and Dissemination plan and also to benefit every partner with impact and awareness. Section 7 summarizes the main conclusions of the document.

The picture below presents the relation among WP7 with the rest of Sodalite WP's:

Figure 1 Relation of WP7 with other WPs

WP7 is an interdependent component within the project work plan and aims at ensuring the maximum impact of the project for interested parties outside of the consortium versus creating the integrity and consistency of all communication and dissemination efforts to achieve the goals mentioned above. In this context, Work Package 7 will work in close collaboration with all project's WPs to ensure that all up to date information and knowledge produced within the project will be effectively recognized and disseminated. WP7 will pursue a minimal impact of the project for all the parties involved and affected by its activity over defining a business plan for exploitable results. The Business Impact strategy among other purposes will promote high credibility within the European software industry, foster alliances with other complementary projects, industry partners and standard bodies and will execute a tailored IPR management strategy for the components and results of the project.

2 Communication and Dissemination Plan

2.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan- Overview Statement

A communication and dissemination plan has a special focus when we work for European funding projects and especially by the fact that we are communicating and disseminating a product that is not 100% developed to be launched in the market and during the first periods of the project life, there are no tangible results to share with our audience.

For this main reason, the SODALITE Communication and Dissemination plan is particularly different and have special requirements.

A Communication and Dissemination Plan is composed of these variables:

1. **Management:** The purpose of this step is to guarantee a good account of resources. (Employees, budget, duration of campaign...)
2. **Objectives:** To efficiently utilize resources, a series of objectives that could be quantitative or qualitative must be defined. E.g. Reach 2500 visitors on our website during Y1.
3. **Target audience:** This variable is with difference essential to obtain successful results. The audience in SODALITE must be different for Dissemination and Communication. The main reason is that the interest of both audiences in the project is different and the channels used to send the message of SODALITE are different, as well. From now on, SODALITE will classify the audience in two different groups (**Dissemination public and Communication audience**). On one hand, *dissemination public* aims to a specific group of people who are highly related to software & computing technologies. Organizations that belong to the dissemination audience are part of scientific fields and academic institutions. Approaching this public will enrich SODALITE by the fact of they have very high expertise in technical development and are very used to contributing open source tools. On the other hand, communication audience is composed by two groups; a general audience not necessarily related with the project at all technical level and the industrial stakeholders which are represented by companies all around the globe providing HPC, Edge computing technologies, IoT solutions or support and Cloud and Software computing products.
4. **The message:** It is necessary to develop a tailored message with all the information of SODALITE that will be launched to the audience. In the case of communication, the language of the content must be adapted to the general public, companies and non-specialized people in software engineering, so far. In the other case, dissemination is focused on scientific academia, expert communities and research groups, so the message is forced to be spoken at a high technical level.
5. **Media and channels:** These are the selected media and channels used to spread the message of SODALITE. To sum up, Twitter, LinkedIn, Website, Press Release, Newsletter, Events and publications, are mainly the ones chosen for this activity. (Find more detailed information in section 3,4 & 5).
6. **Monitoring and follow up:** After setting up the strategy, it is highly recommended to monitor how the actions are responding. For this, SODALITE offers mechanisms to the partners to report all the ongoing activities.

2.2 Dissemination Objectives and KPIs

The Dissemination objectives pursue a seamless publication in academic and scientific journals/platforms and significant presence of the SODALITE team in several events, conferences or Workshops during Y1.

The dissemination strategy pursues to engage with scientific and technical audiences across academia, European organizations and scientific communities. Thus, with the consortium's presence in events (conferences, fairs and workshops) and with publications by our experts in these matters (Software, cloud computing, IaC...), the partners pursue to raise awareness on SODALITE. To achieve this goal, the following metrics have been identified:

KPI	Target Metrics (36 months)	Target Metrics Y1
Scientific Papers	10	4
Presentations, Workshops at conferences, events	30	10
Significant presence at events	12	4
Training/ workshops	1	1

Figure 2 Dissemination KPI's along the project life and Y1

For Y1, the objectives are summarized in:

- Scientific Papers: 4
- Presentations, Workshops at conferences, events: 10
- Significance presence at events: 4
- Training/Workshops: 1

2.3 Communication Objectives and KPIs

The Communication objectives pursue to increase the visibility of project results by showing valuable information regarding the project and its network. The objective is to reach as maximum as possible a diverse audience. Bearing in mind that our key audience is joining scientific/academia and European parties, it is very important to aim toward third parties which can be interested in exploiting our results so far.

The communication actions aim to get visibility, impact and, at a mid-long term, loyalty and engagement. The SODALITE Communication strategy pursues to engage with a wide audience across the world, not only scientific and academia groups but also private companies/organizations and other projects that can benefit from our results and that can be of relevance for SODALITE exploitation and impact plan.

KPI	Target Metrics (36 months)	Target Metrics Y1
Whitepapers	3	1
Press releases	15	5
Website visits	3.000	1.000
Presence in social media (Twitter & LinkedIn)	250 followers	50

KPI	Target Metrics (36 months)	Target Metrics Y1
New blog post	36	12
Relevant guest bloggers	12	4
Significance presence at events	5	3

Figure 3 Communication KPI 's along the project life

For the Y1, the objectives are summarized in:

- Whitepapers: 1 (aims: concept)
- Press release: 5 (See more in section 4.1)
- Website visits: 1000
- Presence in Social Media (Twitter and LinkedIn): 50 followers
- News blog post: 12
- Relevant guest bloggers: 4
- Significant presence at events: 3

3 Off-line Strategy

3.1 SODALITE Branding

SODALITE is defined as “Software Defined Application Infrastructures management and Engineering”.

First of all, a brand book is an essential starting point to define when a company is newly established in the market or on the contrary, it can also work for a new product. By the experts, a brand book is defined as “essentially a set of rules that explain how your brand works (also commonly referred to as a “brand guidelines”, “brand standards,” or a “style guide”)¹.

Before developing the Brand Book of SODALITE, it has been essential to consult existing recommendations from audiovisual and communication both internal (Digital Design support team of Atos) and external sources (Online blogs and media companies), For SODALITE it is mandatory to have a brand book with the intention to facilitate the world that the project is recognised and well accepted in terms of the public image by its audience and followers. The colours, logo and slogan, among others, are helpful to get brand awareness. Additionally, in the process to build our brand book, two blocks have been created in order to include different elements inside them², as experts guidelines suggest:

1. *Philosophy, personality and promise*: This block gathers the central creative concept that would be the **slogan** (Software Defined AppLIcations Infrastructures management and Engineering) and the **keywords** associated with our brand and the meaning of the project content (Software, cloud, IaC, Open Source Software, Software Architectures, Software notation & tools, Software Design & Development). These keywords can help to identify the brand in other channels such as social networks, (project hashtags for Twitter other hashtags to mention in the project publications).
2. *Visual Identity*: In this second block the SODALITE **logo** is included, which was already established months before starting the project (shown below).

Figure 4 SODALITE logo

The colours will be the range of colours used in both print and digital media to represent SODALITE, it is always recommendable to have available a palette of colours to be identified by others and also to attract our followers in all media.

¹ brandmakernews.com/top-stories/7209/why-your-business-needs-a-brand-book.html

² <https://creatibo.arrontesybarrera.com/blog/como-hacer-un-brand-book-para-tu-marca>

Figure 5 Color Palette for SODALITE

Typography is the font style for all the texts that are generated, in this case, the chosen font has been Arvo (see below in Figures 6 and 7).

ARVO FONT
(Copyright (c) 2010-2013, Anton Kovit (anton@korkork.com), with Reserved Font Name Arvo)

Sodalite

Arvo

Figure 6 Main Font of SODALITE₃

fuentes: Arvo
sion 1.004 2010 beta release
ntornos

ghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOI
7890.;; ' " (!?) +-/=*

oz murciélago hindú comía feliz cardillo y kiwi. La cigüeña t
eloz murciélago hindú comía feliz cardil
veloz murciélago hindú com ía

Figure 7 ARVO font Italic

Finally, the **visual style** includes how the elements are displayed on the web, the colour matching in all our channels, videos, images that we upload to our platforms, brochures, posters, among other elements.

3.2 Marketing Material

The following section describes the printed dissemination material prepared by the Communication Team of the project in order to spread the message of SODALITE. This material can be exploited at

³ <https://www.ffonts.net/Arvo.font?text=Sodalite#>

different scenarios such as workshops, business meetings, conferences and fairs, among many others.

Below is presented the first version of the SODALITE brochure. In this first version the information that the consortium decided to show is a presentation of the consortium members and an overview of the objectives and benefits of SODALITE, at a glance:

Figure 8 SODALITE outside page of the brochure

Figure 9 SODALITE inside page of the brochure

The poster has been developed as an overview of the brochure. It shows a description of the consortium and the main objectives of the project, including the same logo and brand guidelines of SODALITE.

Simplify & fully exploit benefits of heterogeneous platforms

SODALITE aims to support development and operation teams in exploiting heterogeneity.

SODALITE provides application developers and infrastructure operators with tools that abstract their application and infrastructure requirements to enable simpler and faster development, deployment, operation, and execution of heterogeneous applications reflecting diverse circumstances over heterogeneous, software-defined, high-performance, cloud infrastructures, with a particular focus on performance, quality, manageability, and reliability.

www.sodalite.eu

info@sodalite.eu

@SODALITESW

SODALITE.EU

This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 825480

Figure 10 SODALITE poster

The invitation card appears as an idea to make the project more professional and a way to get in contact with stakeholders or potential clients. This card is presented in a perfect size to be carried:

Figure 11 SODALITE card

3.3 Project Official presentation

The SODALITE PowerPoint presentation will be part of the different dissemination tools designed to support the SODALITE dissemination toolkit. This presentation aims to be a general overview of the project, including the profile of the consortium, the project’s objectives, motivation, vision and mission, the context where is working and the expected impact, mainly.

It will be used in every event and meeting where SODALITE has a presence. The presentation will follow the identity guidelines, above mentioned, to keep in sense with SODALITE graphic identity guidelines.

Figure 12 SODALITE Official Presentation

4 On-Line Strategy

4.1 Website (Blog, Newsletter/ Press releases)

The SODALITE **website** is one of the main channels to disseminate and communicate the outcomes of the project. The website is available for external users and visitors since the project started in February 2019. The site is concerned with the brand guidelines and image of SODALITE. The website has been developed in Drupal 8. However, the website still needs improvements, more content and updates that will be provided alongside the course of the project during its life.

The URL of the official webpage is www.sodalite.eu. the picture below shows the Home page layout:

Figure 13 Website Main Menu: Announcement of project beginning.

The website follows the EU recommendation regarding usability and accessibility and it includes the logo of the European Commission.

Furthermore, the website contains two main elements through which the consortium will communicate and disseminate what is happening in the project, in terms of technical outcomes and general information (e.g. software, consortium's news or particular hits of interests for SODALITE stakeholders and our partners):

- **Newsletter:** A newsletter is a proper means to carry out direct proactive communications to our targeted audience. There is a calendar plan to be followed by the consortium, in order to update the subscribers with periodical news. For Y1, there are not too much information and advances yet. The Communication and Dissemination plan plans to produce 2 newsletters in Y1. The first newsletter will include more general content about the project and objectives and the second one will refer to, first advances in SODALITE.
- **Blog:** The SODALITE website will offer a Blog section covering different topics such as technologies, methodologies and components used in the project development software updates and others. The Communication and Dissemination strategy plans to produce 12 blog posts in Y1.

Five **Press Release**, shown in the calendar below, will be generated in Y1 to inform about the benefits that SODALITE can offer to the stakeholder groups identified in Communication and Dissemination Plan, detailed in section 2.1

#	Main Objective	Date	Language
1	Project Launch: Objectives & mission, funding and partners.	M3	English, Spanish, Slovenian, Italian, German and Greek and Hebrew
2	SODALITE results in Y1 (Architecture, Use cases)	M12	English, Spanish...

Table 1 Press Releases Calendar Y1

4.2 Social Media (Twitter & LinkedIn)

Social media are another channel to engage with stakeholders and communicate SODALITE objectives, parties and results. The consortium has set up both accounts on Twitter and LinkedIn. The SODALITE social media presence will broaden the reach to the audience and experts interested in following the project. In addition, these types of channels offer the possibility to interact with the followers, getting feedback and suggestions.

The twitter account is managed by Atos and every partner contributes with contents as well as they act as multipliers by inviting their contacts to follow the official project account (@SODALITESW); twitter.com/SODALITESW.

Figure 14 Twitter main menu

To ensure that the SODALITE social media presence is noticed in the relevant communities the consortium will start its presence by inviting their networks to connect with our social media, Twitter and LinkedIn. SODALITE will also actively contribute to relevant social media groups into the area of European Commission Research Field, Open software groups & communities, software companies,

Digital industry, Cloud technologies among other groups to be heard and seen by relevant experts and representatives.

Besides furthering the dissemination of knowledge and experience, this social media can directly contribute to improving the SODALITE project by providing continuous feedback that is essential for guaranteeing the delivery of useful, actionable results directly to the practitioners.

The LinkedIn page is managed by Atos and every partner contributes with content. Moreover, the partners act as multipliers by inviting their contacts to follow the official project group: SODALITE.EU

Figure 15 LinkedIn Page; SODALITE.EU

The SODALITE presence in social media will allow making a rough estimate on how innovative, substantiated and valuable the views are expressed by consortium members and outside stakeholders, e.g. by the number of hits/visits, ‘likes,’ etc. A further advantage of the presence of SODALITE in social media is that these social media groups outlive the duration of the project and help to transfer the SODALITE network to a broader interdisciplinary network that dynamically continues after the completion of the project.

4.3 Other Channels of Communication & Dissemination

This section includes all external communications that somehow are additional to our planned activities. This kind of external actions helps us to gain more visibility out of our efforts and far from our impact expectations.

As an example, Atos has contributed to this section including the SODALITE announcement of the project start at the Atos Research and Innovation monthly Newsletter.

Sodalite

The project has started!

The SODALITE Project held its Kick-off Meeting in Milano last month! The project aims at providing application developers and infrastructure operators the right tools that abstract the requirements to enable simpler and faster development, deployment, operation, and execution of heterogeneous applications reflecting diverse circumstances over heterogeneous, software-defined, high-performance, cloud infrastructures, with a focus on performance quality, manageability, and reliability. SODALITE also proposes to tackle the complexity of deploying and operating modern applications onto heterogeneous HPC and cloud-based software-defined infrastructures, under arbitrary operational conditions and requirements, by achieving tangible business value through effectiveness, flexibility, deployment continuity, and speed.

The 3-year project has a consortium composed by XLAB, HLRS, POLIMI, ADAPTANT, CRAY, IBM, CERTH, and JADS, where the **Advanced Parallel Computing Lab** contributes to the definition and implementation of the SODALITE DSL for the specification of complex distributed software applications and multi-platform delivery infrastructures, including HPC, Cloud, Edge, and IoT; and to the development of the Sodalite IDE and its textual/graphical editors for the Sodalite DSL. In addition, the Lab provides its orchestrator technologies for HPC and Cloud, applying time series forecasting algorithms for determining decision trade-offs and decision making, while monitoring different infrastructure devices and providing adaptation of applications via migration of resources to different hosts.

The project has two special requests for the ARI Team:

1. Follow them on the Social Networks listed below
2. Fill the survey about "[Infrastructure-As-Code \(IaC\) Adoption, Practices and Challenges](#)" that will help them to understand the current adoption of IaC tools and languages for the further development of the project - The survey is available only on Google Forms so remember to change the proxy settings to access!

The team working in this project is composed by **María Martínez Carbonell (Member of the Project Management Committee)**, **Mayte García**, **Román Sosa**, **Yosu Gorroñoigoitia**, **Ricardo Tejada**, **Enrique Martínez**, and **Javier Carnero**.

@SODALITESW

SODALITE.EU

SODALITE Website

Figure 16 Atos ARI Newsletter – SODALITE article

Moreover, SODALITE has been added in ARI Booklet, within Advanced Parallel Computing Lab, along with other relevant projects where this lab is participating: booklet.atosresearch.eu/content/advanced-parallel-computing-0

5 Events and Publications

5.1 Events

This section provides information about the conferences, workshops and all the events that our consortium has expressed an interest to participate, coordinate and organize. The following table depicts a preliminary list for Y1, along with details about the benefit for the project, the impact expected, etc.

EVENT	PLACE	DATE	DESCRIPTION	DISSEMINATION OR COMMUNICATION INTEREST	URL
TU-Automotive Europe 2019	Munich (DE)	29-30/10/2019	Large European Auto Tech event for connected cars, mobility & autonomous vehicles	Exhibiting and pitching SODALITE technology	https://automotive.knect365.com/tu-auto-europe/
SYSTOR 2019	Haifa (IL)	3-5/06/2019	ACM International Systems and Storage Conference	International forum for interaction across the systems research community	https://www.systor.org/2019/
ESEC/FSE 2019	Tallinn (Estonia)	26-30/08/2019	ACM Joint European Software Engineering Conference and Symposium on the Foundations of Software Engineering	International conference on software engineering	https://esec-fse19.ut.ee/
ASE 2019	San Diego (CA)	11-15/11/2019	34th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering	International conference on software engineering	https://2019.ase-conferences.org/
PASC19	ETH Zurich (ETH)	16-20/06/2019	Platform for Advanced Scientific Computing (PASC) Conference	PASC is an international and interdisciplinary platform for the exchange of competences in scientific computing and computational science, with a	https://pasc19.pasc-conference.org/

EVENT	PLACE	DATE	DESCRIPTION	DISSEMINATION OR COMMUNICATION INTEREST	URL
				strong focus on methods, tools, algorithms, application challenges, and novel techniques and usage of high-performance computing.	
ISC 2019	Frankfurt (DE)	16-20/06/2019	European Conference for HPC	Booth with automated SODALITE presentation and key staff for project advertisement.	https://www.isc-hpc.com
SC 2019	Denver (USA)	17-22/11/2019	International conference for HPC	Booth with automated SODALITE presentation and key staff for project advertisement	https://sc19.supercomputing.org/

Table 2 Events calendar for Y1.

5.2 Publications

Publications in specialized magazines and scientific papers sent to related events will attract the attention of interested parties and will provide the opportunity to collaborate within the purposes of the SODALITE project. Therefore, the SODALITE consortium will seek to publish the project outcomes through several professional publications targeting a wide range of stakeholders. Some of these publications are listed in the table below:

TITLE	MAIN LEADER	TARGET AUDIENCE	DISSEMINATION OR COMMUNICATION INTEREST	LINK
A Feature-Oriented Approach to Tenant-Driven Customization of Multi-Tenant Service Networks	JADS/UVT	Research Initiatives and Communities	Dissemination and Communication interest	http://conferences.computer.org/scc/2019/

Table 3 Publications calendar for Y1

6 Partners role & involvement in Communication and Dissemination Plan

ATOS: Atos is responsible for the runtime implementation of SODALITE (WP5) and contributes to the definition and implementation of the SODALITE DSL for the specification of complex distributed software applications and multi-platform delivery infrastructures, including HPC, Cloud, Edge, and IoT; and to the development of the Sodalite IDE and its textual/graphical editors for the Sodalite DSL. In addition, Atos provides its orchestrator technologies for HPC and Cloud, applying time series forecasting algorithms for determining decision trade-offs and decision making. Finally, Atos is a member of the PMC (Project Management Committee) and they are leading the task of Dissemination and Evangelization of the project, to produce and develop attractive material to communicate and enhance the potential of SODALITE outside of the consortium. As the Communication Manager for SODALITE, the planning, execution, and monitoring of communication and dissemination activities is the responsibility of Atos.

XLAB: As the leader of the project's exploitation, XLAB will be in continuous sync with the dissemination of the project to help shaping the core message passed to the several identified audiences, but also on how this message is passed and the project is promoted. Moreover, XLAB will engage in the production of market materials to have them better fit to the business development planned within the exploitation effort. In particular, the exposure of the project's results in industrial events through booths or pitch activities is of high relevance for exploitation, potentiating lead generation and identification of business partnerships. Furthermore, XLAB will collaborate in content production for blog and newsletter regarding the technology they develop in SODALITE, as well as sharing news and ideas to be promoted in the social media channels.

CRAY: CRAY is a leader in HPC business and will contribute to the external coverage of the project by supporting the communication and dissemination activities of SODALITE partnership and through communication with its business users and targeted companies, markets, entities. In addition, Cray will support SODALITE's communications on fairs, meetings, events, to influence targeted industry audiences as well as online coverage on social media channels.

ADAPTANT: ADPT is responsible for the management of IPR, and as such, will ensure there exists a mechanism (refer to SODALITE D1.1) in place to resolve conflict issues between IPR and dissemination objectives. ADPT is also the Exploitation and Innovation Manager of the project, and in conjunction with overseeing the execution of the exploitation plan developed in T7.1, will work closely with the Communication Manager to ensure the appropriate promotion and dissemination of project results to support exploitation objectives. Furthermore, as an SME, ADPT will target industry exhibitions and conferences, mostly pertaining to the connected car, mobility and data portability space to display advances made on SODALITE technology throughout the duration of the project.

POLIMI: POLIMI will disseminate SODALITE results and the knowledge acquired during the project through publication in international journals and conferences. Moreover, POLIMI will exploit SODALITE results in its consultancy and industrial training activities where it will foster their application in practical cases. POLIMI will also contribute to exploitation by training masters and PhD students on the project topics and will evolve the project results of its competence in further research activities.

JADS: JADS will disseminate SODALITE results through publications in prestige international (academic) journals and conferences related to software engineering, service computing, cloud computing, and information systems. In addition, we will disseminate the project outcomes via fosters and flyers at the conferences, where we present our research papers. JADS also foresees exploitation of SODALITE results: through its teaching and consulting offer, both to public and

private-industrial education base, and through JADS's considerable network of data-start-ups and spin-offs. SODALITE results can become a key exploitable asset for practical industrial tutorials over software-defined orchestration as a source of several data-intensive challenges and patterns. JADS will also use practical student projects to extend, and/or further evaluate SODALITE solutions at large scale.

HLRS/ STUTTGART UNIVERSITY: As academic partner within the consortium, USTUTT focuses on scientific expertise and knowledge building. Therefore, the following actions are foreseen in order to facilitate efficient dissemination of the project's activities:

- With its professorial chair at the University of Stuttgart, HLRS transfers the knowledge and ideas of the project to interesting students and PhD candidates. In particular, regular lectures are held and state-of-the-art thesis topics for Bachelor, Master and PhD Students will be offered.
- The project findings will be published and presented at well-known conferences such as the Supercomputing Conference, the International Supercomputing Conference or the Euro-Par Conference to achieve the required scientific impact.
- HLRS operates a well-established training centre for academic and industrial users. The new paradigms of the project will be used to enhance the training material and showcase the SODALITE functionality to attract interesting stakeholders.
- HLRS will make use of its public relations department to publish regularly information of the project via press releases, but also in the German InSIDE magazine as well as the HLRS website and in addition, present SODALITE at the HLRS booth at the International Supercomputing Conference and the Supercomputing Conference.
- Finally, SODALITE with its core technologies will be presented in the internal meetings with the HLRS customers and stakeholders to make people aware about the performance and flexibility of state-of-the-art Cloud Computing with its programming and abstraction models.

CERTH: CERTH is a non-profit research organization and as such focuses on research and its dissemination by publishing results in well-known and widely read international scientific journals, and international scientific conferences, particularly those in the semantic knowledge representation and reasoning domains. CERTH research is also presented in workshops and exhibitions, web-based publishing, standards submissions, small seminars and talks organized for specialized audiences. However, the contact with industry and the consequent opportunity to link the activities of Research Organizations with the ability of industry to observe and take advantage of opportunities for exploitation is also sought by CERTH. In addition, CERTH in collaboration with other partners will prepare and staff an appropriate number of exhibition stands, workshops, and demonstration forums such that the technologies are shown to the chosen audiences.

IBM: IBM will target the dissemination of SODALITE results through publications in international cloud related academic and industrial conferences and participation in industry events both outside and inside IBM. IBM Research - Haifa is hosting the 12th ACM International Systems and Storage Conference (SYSTOR 2019) conference (<https://www.systor.org/2019/4>). In addition, IBM will strive to disseminate the project outcomes through interaction with open source communities, improving project visibility and awareness of the project results, especially among developers and operators of cloud native applications and services. IBM will leverage its participation in additional projects to disseminate SODALITE developments and assets among relevant consortia and beyond, striving to achieve collaboration and synergy with those projects.

⁴ Website of SYSTOR Conference, 2019 <https://www.systor.org/2019/4>.

7 Conclusions

This document provides information regarding the activities to be conducted in *T7.1. Dissemination and Evangelization* within *WP7 Impact Generation* and details the framework for diffusing the project concept, ideas and results.

Mainly, the deliverable outlines the resources/channels to be used, which will altogether contribute towards a successful communication and dissemination strategy. The preparation of communication material, such as the project's logo, brochure, press releases, newsletters, etc, will complement these channels. This material will follow the SODALITE graphical identity.

The SODALITE dissemination and communication strategy identifies the project's target audience and puts a specific focus on the mapping and adaptability of the various dissemination and communication activities to the related stakeholders from the identified target audience.

In the context of online channels, apart from the website, social media accounts have been also set up on Twitter and LinkedIn. Twitter will be used to provide short news updates for the project, while the LinkedIn group created for the project will be the place where developers and researchers can "meet" and exchange experiences.

An initial plan for the timing of related activities for the various identified dissemination and communication channels has been also conducted to ensure the maximization of the project's impact.

Due to the nature of SODALITE as a European funded project, special reference is made within the document to clustering activities. The latter concerns the establishment of liaisons with relevant European projects and communities for sharing knowledge and co-disseminating outcomes, finding extended information of this activity in other documents such as D7.2 where the first approach to SODALITE impact strategy is shown.

To conclude, the dissemination strategy further identifies the metrics for monitoring the conduction of dissemination activities and the evaluation of the project progress in this respect.

8 Annex

8.1 Annex

SODALITE 25/03/2019

“Software Defined Application Infrastructures management and Engineering”

SODALITE incorporates faster and easier mechanisms for software developers to abstract their applications, gaining time and reducing costs in the different software life cycle processes.

In recent years the global market has seen a tremendous rise in utility computing, which serves as the back-end for practically any new technology, methodology or advancement from healthcare to aerospace. We are entering a new era of heterogeneous, software-defined and high-performance computer environments.

In this new era of heterogeneous, software-defined and high-performance computer environments, SODALITE, a Research and Innovation Action project (RIA) funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 program, aspires to address this heterogeneity by providing application developers and infrastructure operators with tools that abstract their application and infrastructure requirements to **enable simpler and faster development**, operation, and execution of heterogeneous applications reflecting diverse circumstances over **heterogeneous, software-defined, high-performance, cloud infrastructures**, with a particular focus on performance, quality, manageability, and reliability.

Coordinated by XLAB, SODALITE has been launched in February 2019 with the purpose of offering a new solution in the field of heterogeneous architectures. The project will follow a path to simplify and ease the way developers approach the development of next-generation applications in the upcoming era of Cloud computing and High-Performance Computing (HPC), among others, for the impact in the European Industry.

Because of the impact of heterogeneity on all computing tasks is rapidly increasing, innovative architectures, algorithm and specialized programming environments and tools are needed to efficiently respond to the demands of industry, using new and mixed/diversified parallel architectures. SODALITE will targets an **application for developers** and infrastructure operators to provide a **faster and easier way** to abstract their applications, **gaining time and reducing costs** in different software life cycle processes such as development, deployment, operation and execution. The scenarios when usually developers face the problems are heterogenous and the focus of solutions is on performance, quality, manageability and reliability.

Moreover, SODALITE supports Digital Transformation of European Industry through increasing design and runtime effectiveness of software defined infrastructures, to ensure high-performance execution over dynamic heterogeneous execution environments;

Figure 17 SODALITE first press release 1

Increasing simplicity of modelling application and infrastructures, to improve manageability, collaboration and time to market.

The project coordinator, Daniel Vladužič (XLAB) affirms that “Performance-oriented Infrastructure-as-a-Code in heterogeneous environments is the next step for the modern systems design and overall lifecycle”

With a total budget of 3.650.731,000€, SODALITE will be running for 36 months (February 2019-January 2021) by a multidisciplinary consortium including strong computer science research in Europe (XLAB, Slovenia) a, global service provider (ATOS, Spain), a High-Performance Computing Centre for research and service institution affiliated to the University of Stuttgart (Germany), The Polytechnic University of Milano (Italy), a German SME focused on enabling adaptable and ethical data utilization (ADAPTANT, Germany), a global leader on supercomputing company (CRAY, United Kingdom), IBM Research (Israel), the European network of Cybersecurity centers and competence Hub for innovation and Operations (CERTH, Greece) and finally The European Research Institute in Service Science(UVT-JADS, Netherlands).

For more information on the project, please contact the coordinator Daniel Vladužič (daniel.vladusic@xlab.si) or visit our website www.sodalite.eu. SODALITE is funded by the EC under Grant Agreement 825480.

Figure 18 SODALITE first press release 2